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TEACHER AWARENESS ON ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES AND INTEGRATION PRACTICES: BASIS FOR AN ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to determine the level of awareness of teachers on environmental issues and use these data as basis to develop an environmental program. The researcher decided to adapt the questionnaires from the Lagao Barangay Development Plan 2015 - 2020. The results of the study showed that the teachers have high awareness with regard to population, resources, and pollution issues. They also exhibited the same results on the level of awareness on environmental issues, particularly on the population, resources, and pollution issues. It was revealed that environmental issues are often integrated by the teachers when teaching English, Science and Mathematics subjects leading to greater awareness about the environment. The results of the study were used as basis for the development of the proposed Environmental Education Program that addresses the environmental issues in Barangay Lagao, General Santos City. This program is aligned with the school curriculum that integrates environmental issues in academic subjects such as Mathematics, English, and Science. The program also proposed teacher awareness on environmental issues so that they can infix the importance of environment.

Keywords: teacher awareness, environmental awareness, integration practices, environmental education program, Lagao North District, General Santos City

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